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DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the impact of globalization on the education system, particularly on the process of teaching foreign languages, as well as the reforms being implemented to improve foreign language instruction in Uzbekistan. The article highlights the expansion of international relations, the importance of foreign language proficiency as a requirement of the modern era, and the role of foreign languages in training qualified specialists. It also provides information on the effective cooperation established between Uzbekistan State University of World Languages and other higher education institutions with foreign countries, the introduction of foreign language teaching standards based on the CEFR international framework, and the use of modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies. The article separately examines innovative approaches in foreign language teaching, interactive methods, intercultural communication, and the role of translation activities in societal development. In particular, the social, cultural, and economic significance of foreign language learning in enhancing Uzbekistan's reputation in the international arena is scientifically substantiated.

Keywords: globalization, foreign languages, international cooperation, educational reforms, CEFR, innovative technologies, translation studies, intercultural communication.

INTRODUCTION

One of the key factors of today's globalization process is the ability of peoples and nations to communicate directly with one another, which makes the serious, intensive, and effective learning of foreign languages extremely important. In the current era, the requirement for qualified specialists to know at least one foreign language is not only a necessity but also a means of gaining awareness of global events, developments, innovations, and new ideas. This, in turn, enables individuals to understand developmental trends and keep pace with the times.

Moreover, conducting direct negotiations—without interpreters—with foreign investors and guests visiting Uzbekistan has significant value in strengthening mutual communication and further improving the country’s international image. The relevance of this issue has become particularly evident in recent years due to Uzbekistan’s increasingly active and intensive international relations, meetings, conferences, and seminars. In such interactions, much depends on interpreters, who serve as the main connecting bridge. Translation is a powerful tool that contributes to international friendship, partnership, and cooperation, as well as to the expansion of economic-political, scientific, cultural, and literary relations between nations. The field of translation is so multifaceted that it is difficult to imagine any sphere of life without it [1].

Main Part

The large-scale reforms implemented in Uzbekistan in recent years have led to significant achievements that are widely recognized by the international community. Particularly noteworthy are the practical efforts aimed at improving education, introducing modern pedagogical technologies into language teaching, and enabling learners to acquire language skills based on global and European educational standards. These measures have strengthened Uzbekistan’s position on the international stage.

Commenting on these developments, R. Krishnan, Chairman of the Gandhi Memorial Foundation from Malaysia, stated: *“Every time I visit Uzbekistan, I am impressed by the achievements in all sectors, especially in education. I am particularly astonished by the level of attention given to foreign language learning. Seeing that your youth can speak many foreign languages—and English in particular—so freely truly impressed me. Introducing English language instruction from the first grade is a very commendable initiative aimed at ensuring the country’s bright future and supporting the intellectual development of the young generation.”*

Similarly, Chinese scholar Li Si, Director of the Central Asian Institute at Shaanxi Pedagogical University, emphasized that Uzbekistan’s reputation in the world, including within the system of international relations, is steadily growing. He noted that Uzbekistan possesses enormous potential, and therefore many countries seek to expand cooperation with your nation [2].

If we look back at the history of foreign language education in Uzbekistan, we see that Western languages such as German, English, French, and Spanish, as well as Eastern languages such as Arabic, Persian, Hindi, Chinese, and Korean, have been taught here for almost one hundred years [3]. Foreign language instruction initially began at Tashkent and Samarkand State Universities and later continued at the Tashkent State Pedagogical Institute. A major historical contribution to improving the teaching of foreign languages was the establishment of the Tashkent Pedagogical

Institute of Foreign Languages, founded in accordance with the Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR dated 25 August 1948 [4]. At that time, there was proportional balance among the languages taught, and nearly equal quotas were allocated for each. Russian, in particular, was taught in Uzbek schools almost as a second native language.

Through foreign languages, one becomes aware of the innovations driving global progress, and opportunities arise to stay in step with international development. At the same time, foreign languages make it possible to promote a nation's rich culture to the world, follow socio-political changes, and introduce the national education system to the global community—requirements that are dictated by the modern era.

Indeed, as socio-economic processes in the country rise to a new stage and become a decisive force, Uzbekistan's international prestige and standing continue to grow. In particular, at the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages—considered the leading higher educational institution specializing in foreign languages—extensive work has been carried out to further improve language teaching and learning, and to enhance the qualifications of specialists being trained in this field.

Since 2001, in cooperation with foreign experts, 150 students with strong ability in English were selected and enrolled in a special program—the ELIT Department, later reorganized into the IELTE (Institute for English Language Teacher Education), where they studied English using interactive methods. All instructors of IELTE underwent specialized training courses and began teaching the new curriculum exclusively in English through interactive methodology. More than 20 specialists from the United Kingdom, the United States, Hungary, Turkey, and New Zealand taught at the department. Through the support of embassies and international organizations, meetings with students were organized, and more than 2,500 textbooks, scientific works, and works of literature were brought to the institution [5].

The university maintains effective cooperation with many prominent higher education institutions around the world, including Ruhr and Heidelberg Universities in Germany; the University of Vienna in Austria; the Universities of Granada, Madrid, Barcelona, Complutense Madrid, and Juan Carlos in Spain; the University for Foreigners in Perugia, Italy; the Higher Institute of Translation in Belgium; the Universities of Athens and Ioannina in Greece; the International Technical College in New Zealand; Pusan, Chung-Ang, Honam, Inha, Jongbu and Seoul National University of Education in Korea; Cairo, Ain Shams, and Banha Universities in Egypt; the Universities of Malaya and Perlis in Malaysia; the Moscow State Linguistic University and the A.S. Pushkin State Institute of the Russian Language in Russia. In addition to cooperation in the field of education, mutually beneficial agreements have also been signed covering scientific and practical activities.

Furthermore, work has been carried out jointly with international organizations from foreign countries, including the British Council (UK), DAAD (Germany), AESI (Spain), KOICA (South Korea), JAICA (Japan), TIKA (Turkey), the Victor Hugo Cultural Center (France), the Egyptian Cultural Center, the Lal Bahadur Shastri Cultural Center (India), and the Greek Cultural Center. The university has also participated in European Union grant programs. For example, it regularly received international grants under the TEMPUS program. Until 2007, the university successfully participated in four TEMPUS projects. In 2007, it obtained the international grant TEMPUS SCM TO49A06 BOLERO titled “The Bologna Process and Reforms in Higher Education in Uzbekistan” under the TEMPUS program. This project was implemented in cooperation with Marc Bloch University and the University of Strasbourg (France), the University of Leipzig (Germany), Comenius University in Bratislava (Slovakia), and the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages [6].

The intensification of such cooperative relations demonstrates that specialists trained in foreign languages in Uzbekistan are capable of competing on equal terms with professionals from any other country. Particularly in the context of globalization and the growing importance of international relations, the improvement of foreign language teaching and learning, as well as the increasing attention devoted to language education, play a key role in enriching public consciousness, expanding intellectual horizons, and strengthening national identity.

Undoubtedly, the Presidential Decree No. PQ-1875 of December 10, 2012, “On Measures for Further Improvement of the System of Learning Foreign Languages” [7], clarified the scope of necessary actions in this field. Following this decree, the main goals were to modernize the education system, introduce foreign language teaching based on modern pedagogical and information-communication technologies, radically improve the training of specialists capable of communicating freely in foreign languages, enable the younger generation to access global scientific achievements and world information resources, and promote international cooperation and communication. In accordance with the decree, State Educational Standards for foreign languages were developed and approved, and it was planned that from 2013 onward, the teaching of foreign languages in public schools would begin from Grade 1.

At that time, foreign languages were taught in all 9,692 general secondary schools of the republic: English in 8,543 schools to 3.01 million students, German in 1,589 schools to 316,000 students, French in 1,076 schools to 216,000 students, and other languages (Spanish, Hindi, Arabic, Korean, Chinese) in 27 schools to 6,300 students. During that academic year, 631,200 first-graders, 583,500 second-graders, and 539,300 third-graders studied foreign languages (94.2% English, 3.4% German, 2.4% French)

[8]. This was undoubtedly a requirement of the time.

However, the decree's emphasis on the word "primarily" in reference to which foreign languages should be taught—directed mainly at English—caused considerable debate. This was justified by English being an international language. As a result, English language instruction was introduced as the main foreign language in all general education institutions. German and French teachers working in schools were required to attend short-term training courses and obtain English-language teaching certificates, otherwise they were to be dismissed. Not everyone was prepared for such requirements. Consequently, nearly 5,000 German and French teachers were dismissed. This increased the already growing social issue of unemployment, now including highly educated and qualified professionals. Even if English were to be prioritized nationwide, such changes should have been introduced gradually rather than in such a unilateral manner [9].

Currently, there are several internationally recognized testing systems used around the world to determine foreign language proficiency levels, such as IELTS, TOEFL, and CEFR. Therefore, it is not enough to simply know a foreign language; rather, it is essential to master it at a level that meets global standards. The standards of Uzbekistan's continuous education system were developed based on the requirements of the Council of Europe's "Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment (CEFR)." To ensure that the State Educational Standards were thoroughly and properly designed, an expert group led by British specialists Rod Bolbayto and Davis Alan was invited [10].

In Uzbekistan, foreign language instruction has been largely structured in accordance with CEFR test requirements, with language proficiency developed through the stages of A1, A1+, A2, B1, B1+, B2, and C1. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 124 of May 8, 2013, "On Approving the State Educational Standard for Foreign Languages in the System of Continuous Education" [11], the B1 and B1+ levels of foreign language proficiency were established for secondary specialized and vocational education. In collaboration with international experts, new State Educational Standards and curricula were created in line with CEFR requirements, and textbooks for Grades 1 and 4 were authored by local specialists, taking into account the psychological and age-related characteristics of schoolchildren. These textbook sets were reviewed and refined by foreign experts through cooperation with the British Council in Tashkent, the Goethe Institute, and the Embassy of France.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the reforms implemented to improve the foreign language teaching system in Uzbekistan have played an important role in strengthening the country's

prestige within the international community. In the context of globalization, the expansion of international cooperation, the study of advanced foreign experience, and the introduction of global standards into the education system have significantly enhanced the content and quality of foreign language instruction.

The effective partnerships established between the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, other higher education institutions, and foreign universities have created opportunities to train a new generation equipped with modern knowledge and skills, capable of competing on the global stage. In addition, the adoption of Presidential Decree PQ-1875 and the development of educational standards based on the international CEFR framework marked the beginning of a new phase in foreign language teaching.

However, the exclusive emphasis on English at the expense of other languages and the resulting reduction of employment opportunities for teachers of German, French, and other languages indicates the need for a more balanced approach in the future. It is crucial to recognize that every foreign language plays an important role in enhancing cultural, economic, and political ties between nations.

Overall, Uzbekistan's reforms in foreign language education and its active participation in international cooperation not only contribute to the modernization of the national education system but also play a significant role in fostering a globally minded younger generation.

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